

Discrete Element Modelling of Rock Drilling

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ABSTRACT

Percussive rotary drilling is recognized as the most efficient method for hard rock drilling. Despite clear advantages over conventional rotary methods, there are still some uncertainties associated with percussive drilling. For geothermal applications, drilling accounts for a large portion of the total cost. Specifically, the wear of drill bits when drilling in hard rock is a predominant cost factor and drilling parameters are often based on the experience of the field operator. Within the framework of the H2020 project GEOFIT, numerical simulations of percussive drilling are performed in order to evaluate the rock drilling process and gain insight about the trade-off between wear and Rate of Penetration (ROP). In the simulations, the rock material was represented by the Bonded Discrete Element Method (BDEM), the drill bit by the Finite Element Method (FEM), the drilling fluid by the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) and the abrasive wear on the surface of the drill bit was represented by Archard's wear law. The drilling simulations were conducted for two rock materials; a sedimentary rock material corresponding to what was found when drilling at the GEOFIT pilot site in Aran Islands, Ireland, and a harder reference rock similar to granite. The results show that, at a drill bit impact force of 10 kN, the ROP in the sedimentary rock was 6.3 times faster than for granite. When increasing the impact force to 40 and 50 kN, however, the ROP for the sedimentary rock is only 1.9 and 1.6 times faster, respectively. Furthermore, the wear rate decreased with increased impact force when drilling in the granite rock. For the sedimentary rock, however, the loading resulting in the best trade-off between abrasive wear and ROP was the second highest loading of 40 kN, which suggests that an increase in impact energy may increase the rate of penetration but may not be economically motivated.

1. INTRODUCTION

The process of rock drilling is used for several applications, e.g., mining, exploration and geothermal installation. Percussive Rotary Drilling (PRD) is recognized as the most efficient method for drilling in hard rock, with the down-the-hole (DTH) method being most common. Here, the drill bit is typically made from high-strength low alloy-steel with cemented carbide inserts situated at the face of the bit. A piston strikes the tail of the bit, generating a compressive stress wave that propagates through the bit, pushing the cemented carbide inserts into the surface of the rock. This induces microcracks on the rock surface that subsequently develops into major cracks that removes chips of rock from the surface. These chips are then flushed from the hole using compressed fluids (typically air or water). Since the drill bit is rotating, the bit strikes a new rock surface with the next impact and the process is repeated. It is well known that the initiation and propagation of cracks are governing factors for rock excavation processes (Saadati 2015; Saksala et al. 2018; Shariati 2019)

The PRD method has been shown to be between 2.3 to 7.3 times faster than rotary methods and experiences less abrasive wear due to less contact time with the rock surface (Melamed et al. 1997). Although having clear advantages, the PRD method still has some uncertainties associated with it. By increasing the impact force, for example, an increase in ROP may be obtained, but the potential increase of the wear rate might not be economically motivated. The wear of drill bits is a predominant cost factor of geothermal installation, partly due to unexpected maintenance and partly due to the loss in efficiency when drilling with a worn out bit (DiPippo 2016; Plinninger 2008). Drilling parameters are often based on the experience of the field operator rather than scientific theory. By utilizing numerical models and simulation, an increased knowledge and understanding of rock drilling can be obtained and aid in optimizing the process.

The process of rock drilling includes several physical phenomena, such as contact between drill bit and rock,

but also the interaction between drilling fluid, equipment and rock cuttings. Therefore, the simulation of rock drilling requires the use of multiple numerical approaches in order to capture the complexity of the process. In this work, the multiphysics nature of PRD is achieved by coupling numerical models. The Bonded Discrete Element Method (BDEM) is used to model the rock material, the Finite Element Method (FEM) for the drill bit and the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) for the drilling fluid. Furthermore, the qualitative abrasive wear on the surface of the drill bit is obtained through Archard's abrasive wear law. The relation between drill bit impact force and drilling performance, in terms of wear rate and ROP, is evaluated for two rock materials.

2. METHODOLOGY

The methodology used for simulating the rock drilling process is multiphysical. This includes coupling between the applied numerical methods, i.e., the DEM, BDEM, FEM and PFEM, as well as a procedure used for calibrating the micromechanical rock material model.

2.1 Discrete Element Method

The DEM was originally formulated by Cundall & Strack (1979) and is commonly applied for simulation of industrial problems involving granular assemblies, such as milling and mining applications (Larsson et al 2021). Here, the material is represented by a set of rigid, spherical particles. The motion of each particle is tracked using Newton's second law

$$m_i \frac{dv_i}{dt} = F_i \quad [1]$$

where m_i and v_i are the mass and velocity of particle i , respectively. The total force F_i acting on particle i is given by

$$F_i = F_i^{ext} + \sum_{j=1}^{n_j} F_{ij} \quad [2]$$

where F_i^{ext} are the external forces, such as gravity, n_j is the number of neighbouring particles and F_{ij} is the contact force between particle i and j . The angular motion is governed by

$$I_i \frac{d\omega_i}{dt} = \sum_j M_{ij} \quad [3]$$

where I_i and ω_i is the moment of inertia and angular velocity of particle i respectively. The applied torque from particle j on particle i is given by M_{ij} . The contact forces between particles are in this work represented by a linear spring-dashpot model for both the normal and tangential direction. There are essentially six parameters governing the behavior of the DEM; normal and shear spring constants, k_n and k_s , normal and shear damping coefficients, c_n and c_s , dry friction between the particles μ_{p-p} as well as dry friction between the drill bit and the particles μ_{b-p} . Equations [1]-[3] are integrated using the explicit integration scheme in LS-DYNA (Livermore Software Technology Corporation

2020), which then gives the velocities and positions of each particle.

2.2 Bonded Discrete Element Method

The BDEM is an extension to the DEM that is widely used to model brittle continuum materials such as rock and cement. In conjunction to the conventional DEM, the BDEM includes linear elastic beams, or *bonds*, between the particles (Potyondy et al. 2004). The normal bond force \overline{F}^n , shear bond force \overline{F}^s , normal bond moment \overline{M}^n and shear bond moment \overline{M}^s are updated incrementally each time step by

$$\Delta \overline{F}^n = \overline{k}^n A \Delta U^n \quad [4]$$

$$\Delta \overline{F}^s = -\overline{k}^s A \Delta U^s \quad [5]$$

$$\Delta \overline{M}^n = -\overline{k}^s J \Delta \theta^n \quad [6]$$

$$\Delta \overline{M}^s = -\overline{k}^n I \Delta \theta^s \quad [7]$$

where \overline{k}^n and \overline{k}^s are the normal and shear bond stiffnesses and $\Delta U^{n/s}$ and $\Delta \theta^{n/s}$ represents the relative incremental displacement and rotation in the normal (n) and shear (s) direction. A bond will break if either the maximum normal stress ($\overline{\sigma}^{max}$) or maximum shear stress ($\overline{\tau}^{max}$) exceeds the prescribed strength value, i.e.,

$$\overline{\sigma}^{max} = \frac{|\overline{F}^n|}{A} + \frac{|\overline{M}^s| \overline{R}}{I} \geq \sigma_c \quad [8]$$

$$\overline{\tau}^{max} = \frac{|\overline{F}^s|}{A} + \frac{|\overline{M}^n| \overline{R}}{J} \geq \tau_c \quad [9]$$

where A is the bond area and I and J are the moment and polar moment of inertia of the bond. The pre-described normal and shear strength values are represented by σ_c and τ_c , respectively. Energy dissipation, from e.g., internal friction, is governed by a local non-viscous damping $\overline{\alpha}$, and the amount of particle interlocking is controlled via the interlocking range $\overline{\beta}$. Thus, the BDEM has a total of 12 input parameters, six of which are related to the conventional DEM formulation (k_n , k_s , c_n , c_s , μ_{p-p} and μ_{b-p}) and six of which are related to the BDEM (\overline{k}^n , \overline{k}^s , σ_c , τ_c , $\overline{\alpha}$ and $\overline{\beta}$). The calibration and motivation for the chosen values of these parameters are presented in Section 2.4.

2.3 Particle Finite Element Method

The main idea for the PFEM is the combination of a Lagrangian FEM formulation together with a powerful remeshing strategy and was originally developed for fluid-structure interactions and free surface fluid flow (Idelsohn et al. 2004; Idelsohn et al. 2006). In LS-DYNA, the fluid is considered incompressible, which reduces the governing equations for the fluid flow to (Livermore Software Technology Corporation, 2014)

$$\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_i} = 0 \quad [10]$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial t} + u_i \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} \right) = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \mu \frac{\partial^2 u_i}{\partial x_j \partial x_j} + \rho f_i \quad [11]$$

where u_i are the velocity components and x_i represents the spatial coordinates. The hydrostatic pressure is represented by p , the dynamic fluid viscosity by μ , the volumetric mass density by ρ and the components of external body forces by f_i . Although the PFEM allows for remeshing of the fluid domain, a simplified approach without remeshing is used in this work. Further, no FSI exists between the drilling fluid and the drill bit. The interaction between the fluid and the rock cuttings is represented by a two-way coupling between the PFEM and DEM models. The DEM affect the fluid flow by adding velocities and masses of the particles to the body forces f_i in the governing equation [11]. The fluid flow around the particles is represented by a potential flow around a sphere. Here, the drag force is given by

$$f_d = \frac{1}{2} v^2 A \rho C_d \quad [12]$$

where v is the relative velocity between fluid and particle, A is the projected surface area, ρ is the volumetric mass density of the fluid and $C_d = 0.5$ is the drag coefficient.

2.4 Rock material calibration

At the GEOFIT pilot site in Aran Islands, drilling was conducted on a sedimentary rock. As input data for this type of rock, high strain rate experimental data from literature is used (Cai et al. 2007). Here, the authors obtained an increase of the compressive and tensile strength for sedimentary rock at different strain rates. At strain rates of $\dot{\epsilon} \sim 10$ to 100 s^{-1} , assumed to be representative of the strain rates during percussive rotary drilling, the compressive and tensile strength of the materials was obtained, see Table 1. As a reference to the sedimentary rock, a harder granite rock material was also simulated within this work. The dynamic compressive and tensile strength of the granite rock was obtained using a Split-Hopkinson Pressure Bar, see (Wessling 2021). Both rock materials are assumed to have an elastic modulus of 30 GPa.

Table 1: Compressive and tensile strength values for the rocks simulated in this study.

Test	Sedimentary rock*	Granite rock**
Compressive strength [MPa]	53.4	349.0
Tensile strength [MPa]	8.9	29.7

* Values from (Cai et al. 2007). ** Values from (Wessling 2021).

For the BDEM calibration, the objective is to determine the set of 12 microscopic model parameters that results in the desired macroscopic strengths. This is typically achieved through trial-and-error simulations of laboratory experiments, but this can be time consuming. In this work, the number of parameters obtained from trial-and-error are minimized by using analytical relationships and selecting values from literature. The remaining parameters are determined from simulations of the uniaxial compression test and Brazilian disc test. The normal stiffness of the DEM, for instance, can be prescribed as (Potyondy et al. 2004)

$$k_n = 4RE_c \quad [13]$$

where $E_c = 30 \text{ GPa}$ is the macroscopic modulus and R is the particle radius. The damping parameters c_n , c_s and $\bar{\alpha}$ were all set to 0.7, and the friction between particles were set to $\mu_{p-p} = 0.5$ which is supposed to be representative of rock materials (Potyondy et al. 2004). For the interlocking range, the particles were allowed to form bonds with neighboring particles within one particle diameter, i.e., $\beta = 2R$. With this choice of interlocking range, the amount of particles embedded between two interacting pairs of particles are minimized (Scholtés et al. 2013).

The remaining microscopic parameters, i.e., k_s , \bar{k}^n , \bar{k}^s , σ_c and τ_c , are obtained from simulations of the Uniaxial Compression Test (UCT) and Brazilian Disc Test (BDT). For both tests, the particle radius is uniformly distributed between 0.15 and 0.45 mm, i.e., $R \sim U(0.15, 0.45)$ mm. The calibrated parameters are presented in Table 2. Note that some of the input parameters are expressed in terms of the particle radius R in order to scale the input depending on the choice of particle size. The microscopic parameters for the granite rock was obtained by scaling the parameters for the sedimentary rock with a factor of 6, which resulted in macroscopic strengths consistent with experimental observations.

Table 2: Calibrated input parameters for the BDEM. k_n , k_s and $\bar{\beta}$ are expressed in terms of particle radius R in order to represent different discretizations.

Parameter	k_n [kN/mm]	k_s [kN/mm]	c_n []	c_s []	μ_{p-p} []	μ_{b-p} []	\bar{k}^n [GPa]	\bar{k}^s [GPa]	σ_c [MPa]	τ_c [GPa]	$\bar{\alpha}$ []	$\bar{\beta}$ [mm]
Sedimentary	$120 \cdot 10^9 \cdot R$	$24 \cdot 10^9 \cdot R$	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.5	7.5	1.5	9.6	1.08	0.7	$2 \cdot R$
Granite	$120 \cdot 10^9 \cdot R$	$24 \cdot 10^9 \cdot R$	0.7	0.7	0.5	0.5	7.5	1.5	57.6	6.48	0.7	$2 \cdot R$

2.4.1 Uniaxial Compression Test

In the UCT, a rock materials resistance to compression is measured by loading a cylinder axially until failure. The ultimate compressive strength (UCS) is defined as

$$UCS = \frac{F}{A_0} \quad [14]$$

where F is the load at failure and A_0 is the cross-sectional area of the sample. Using a sample diameter of 25 mm, a height of 50 mm and the model parameters for the sedimentary rock in Table 2, the stress-strain curve to the right in Figure 1 is obtained. This corresponds to a UCS = 55 MPa and an elastic modulus of $E = 31$ GPa, which is considered sufficiently close to the goal of UCS = 53.4 MPa and $E = 30$ GPa.

Figure 1: An example of the simulated uniaxial compression test for the sedimentary rock. The fractured sample (left) and the corresponding stress-strain curve (right).

2.4.2 Brazilian disc test

The BDT is an experimental method for measuring the indirect tensile strength of brittle materials such as rock and concrete. Here, a thin disc is compressed diametrically, inducing an indirect tensile stress field located at a region around the center part of the disc. This induced tensile stress at the center part is given by (Hondros 1959)

$$UTS = \frac{2F}{\pi Dt} \quad [15]$$

where F is the applied load and D and t is the diameter and thickness of the disc, respectively. Using a sample diameter of 25 mm, a thickness of 5 mm and the input

parameters for the sedimentary rock from Table 2, the stress-displacement curve to the right in Figure 2 is obtained. This corresponds to a UTS = 9.4 MPa, which is considered sufficiently close to the goal of UTS = 8.9 MPa.

Figure 2: An example of the simulated Brazilian disc test of the sedimentary rock. The fractured sample (left) and the corresponding stress-displacement curve (right).

2.5 Numerical setup

In Figure 3, an overview of the numerical configuration used for the rock drilling simulations can be seen. A drill bit with a diameter of 130 mm is used. The rock material is represented by two parts. The rock material closest to the drill bit is represented by a cylinder of BDEM with diameter 200 mm. Here, a particle radius distribution of $R \sim U(0.69, 2.07)$ mm (roughly 400,000 particles) is used together with the calibrated model parameters in Table 2. In order to model a larger piece of the ground while maintaining a reasonable computational time, the rock material further away from the drill bit, up to a distance of 1.5 m) is

Figure 3: Numerical setup for the rock drilling simulations. The far field finite element (left) and the bonded discrete element representation of the rock (right).

represented by roughly 140,000 solid tetrahedral finite elements, using a linear-elastic constitutive model with

elastic modulus 30 GPa, Poisson's ratio 0.2 and density 5000 kg/m³. The peripheral FEM-nodes are constrained from movement, while the particles at the BDEM-FEM interface are constrained to the FEM-surfaces. Furthermore, non-reflective boundary conditions are used for the BDEM-FEM interface and peripheral FEM nodes in order to eliminate non-physical wave reflections. The PFEM domain consists of 16,000 solid tetrahedral elements and the fluid is air with density 1.225 kg/m³ and dynamic viscosity 1.81 x 10⁻⁵ kg/ms. A constant flow velocity of 50 m/s is imposed on the fluid, directed up through the borehole. The drill bit geometry is a commercial bit provided by the company responsible for the drilling at Aran Islands. The bit is modelled using 40,000 rigid shell elements with a mass of 25 kg. A rotational velocity of 90 RPM is imposed on the bit and the percussive motion is prescribed on the bit through a specified load versus time curve, see Figure 4. Here, a frequency of 100 Hz was used and a parametric study was conducted on the impact force – 5, 7.5, 10, 40 and 50 kN – which is to be compared to the reported force of 8 kN used in the drilling tests in Aran Islands.

Figure 4: The different loading cases used for the parametric study of drill bit impact force.

The drilling at the pilot site at the Aran Islands resulted in no measurable wear. However, the qualitative drill bit wear is included through Archard's abrasive wear law in the simulations. Here, the wear depth rate on the drill bit is given by (Archard et al. 1956)

$$\dot{h} = \frac{kF_N V_t}{A} \quad [16]$$

where F_N is the normal force of the particle sliding with tangential velocity V_t on the target surface and A is the

Figure 5: The region where the abrasive drill bit wear is measured.

contact area. The wear rate coefficient k could be obtained from tribological testing, however, since no tribological data is available for the sedimentary rock on Aran Islands, the wear rate coefficient was set to $k = 1$. This means the wear results are only qualitative. Comparisons between different drill bit loadings are still possible, however. The wear is measured as the accumulated wear depth for the front part of the bit, i.e., the region inside the red rectangle in Figure 5.

3. Results and discussion

The major results from the multiphysics simulations are presented and discussed. This includes the rock fracture and borehole condition, rate of penetration and consequential wear of the bit as well as the vibrations of the far-field FEM representation of the rock.

3.1 Rock fracture and cutting transport

An example of the fractured rock from different stages of one of the simulations can be seen in Figure 6. Clear indentation marks can be seen from the first few strikes of the drill bit inserts at 50 ms. As the drill bit strikes the surface, rotates, and strikes again, the bit penetrates deeper and the bottom rock surface is somewhat even, i.e., at 150-500 ms. By inspecting the borehole walls at 500 ms, variations of the borehole diameter can be seen. This could be explained by variations of bit striking velocity or heterogeneous particle sizes. In addition, it could be explained by the bit being temporarily stuck at a certain depth due to an excess of rock cuttings, continuously striking cuttings instead of the solid rock surface, which fractures the rock radially. A solution to this could be to increase the fluid flow in the borehole, or by modelling a full FSI-coupling between the fluid and the drill bit, which would create streamlines around the drill bit structure, clearing the borehole more efficiently.

Figure 6: A cross-section view of the rock fracture at 50, 150, 300 and 500 ms. The color of the particles corresponds to the number of broken bonds, e.g., red particles have lost all their bonds with neighbouring particles.

Figure 7: The flow of rock particles in the borehole at 80, 150, 300 and 500 ms. The particle colors represents the velocity in the vertical (x) direction.

An example of the flow of sedimentary rock cuttings in the borehole can be seen in Figure 7 for different stages of simulation. The flow in the borehole is capable of clearing the cuttings sufficiently early on as shown from the simulations, i.e. at 80 and 150 ms. However, as the drill bit penetrates deeper and more cuttings are chipped from the surface, there appears to be a region close to the bit where the rock cutting flow slows down, i.e. at 300 and 500 ms. As mentioned before, this could be solved by improving the fluid flow in the borehole by either increasing the flow velocity or by using a full FSI-coupling with the bit.

3.2 Rate of penetration and wear

The ROP of the different rock materials and load cases are presented in Table 3 while the penetration versus time is shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9 for the sedimentary and granite rock, respectively. For the granite rock, the 5 and 7.5 kN load cases were omitted due to marginal rate of penetration. At 10 kN, the rate of penetration of the sedimentary rock is 6.3 times faster than for the granite rock. At 40 and 50 kN, the rate of penetration of the sedimentary rock is 1.9 and 1.6 times faster, respectively. This suggests that, for a weaker rock, the increased impact energy results in a decreased rate of penetration compared to that of a stronger rock. This could be explained by the drilling fluid not being as efficient at flushing the borehole free of rock cuttings since more of these exists at larger impact forces.

Table 3: Rate of penetration for the different rock types and load cases.

Load [kN]	5	7.5	10	40	50
ROP Sedimentary [m/s]	0.15	0.19	0.25	0.34	0.35
ROP Granite [m/s]	N/A	N/A	0.04	0.18	0.22

Figure 8: Penetration versus time for the sedimentary rock material.

Figure 9: Penetration versus time for the granite rock material.

The qualitative wear versus penetration for the different load cases can be seen in Figures 10 and 11 for the sedimentary and granite rock, respectively, and the wear rates are summarized in Table 4. For the granite rock, it would appear the largest load case of 50 kN is most economically motivated with regards to wear (although the 10 kN case is rather inconclusive here). For the sedimentary rock, however, the second largest load case of 40 kN is most economically motivated. This suggests that an increased impact energy may increase the rate of penetration but may not be economically motivated. By comparing the wear rates for the two rock types at different loads, it is found that the granite wear rate is 3.8, 1.7 and 1.4 times larger than that of the sedimentary rock for 10, 40 and 50 kN, respectively.

Figure 10: Penetration versus time for the granite rock material.

Figure 11: Penetration versus time for the granite rock material.

Table 4: Wear rates for the different rock types and load cases.

Load [kN]	5	7.5	10	40	50
Wear rate Sedimentary [mm ⁻¹]	0.45	0.46	0.50	1.08	1.27
Wear rate granite [mm ⁻¹]	N/A	N/A	1.91	1.82	1.75

3.3 Ground vibrations

For the 50 kN load case, examples of the far-field in-plane displacements in the FEM representation of the sedimentary and granite rock can be seen in Figure 11 and 12, respectively. The in-plane displacement is the largest close to the center part where the drill bit strikes, and displacement waves can be seen to propagate in the radial direction. However, the magnitude of the displacement is marginal with a maximum of roughly 1.5×10^{-4} mm close to the center. Further away from the centre, the wave peaks reach no more than 1.0×10^{-4} mm.

Figure 13: The in-plane displacement (mm) of the far field FEM representation of the sedimentary rock at $t = 250$ ms and with a load of 50 kN.

Figure 12: The in-plane displacement (mm) of the far field FEM representation of the granite rock at $t = 250$ ms and with a load of 50 kN.

4. Conclusions

As a part of the Horizon 2020 project GEOFIT, multiphysics simulations of the rock drilling process have been carried out. The simulations were based on a combined BDEM-FEM approach for the rock material, a FEM representation of the drill bit, a PFEM representation of the drilling fluid (air) and the qualitative abrasive wear of the drill bit surface was accounted for using Archard’s wear law. The rock model was calibrated for two materials; a sedimentary rock similar to the ground conditions at Aran Islands as well as a stronger granite rock used as reference.

The rock material was calibrated for two rock types – a sedimentary rock similar to the ground conditions at Aran Islands as well as a stronger granite rock, experimentally characterized at high strain rates. Using these two calibrated rock models, the effect that impact force has on rate of penetration and drill bit wear was evaluated. Furthermore, the rock fracture and borehole condition were studied as well as the far-field vibrations of the FEM representation of the rock.

The following conclusions can be made from the numerical investigation:

- The BDEM can be calibrated for sedimentary rock and give reasonable compressive and tensile strengths with correct failure modes of the uniaxial compression test and Brazilian disc test. Furthermore, the BDEM-FEM made it possible to study the response of the rock far away from the bit without using computationally demanding particles for the whole domain. The study of far-field rock displacements showed that waves do exist, but with a marginal magnitude of 1.0×10^{-4} mm.
- The numerical study gave insight about the rock fracture in rock drilling, in particular concerning borehole condition. Variations of the borehole diameter are attributed to either particle size heterogeneity or insufficient fluid flow in the borehole.
- The flushing of the borehole was found to be sufficient at early stages of the drilling, but as more rock cuttings are excavated there is a region close to the bit where the flow of rock cuttings slows down. In order to remedy this, it was suggested to increase either the flow velocity or to use a full FSI-coupling between fluid and drill bit.
- At 10 kN impact loading, the rate of penetration of the sedimentary rock was 6.3 times faster than in granite. However, at 40 and 50 kN, the rate of penetration of the sedimentary rock is only 1.9 and 1.6 times faster, respectively. This was concluded to be due to the problem with flushing the rock cuttings from the borehole, which is more prevalent for the weaker sedimentary rock.
- By evaluating the rate of wear, it was found that the wear rate decreased with increased impact loading when drilling in the granite rock. For the sedimentary rock, however, the most economical loading was the second highest loading of 40 kN. This indicates that an increased impact energy may increase the rate of penetration but may not be economically motivated.

REFERENCES

- Archard, J. F., & Hirst, W. (1956). The wear of metals under unlubricated conditions. *Proc. Roy. Soc. A.*, 236(1206), 397–410.
- Cai, M., Kaiser, P. K., Suorinen, F., & Su, K. (2007). A study on the dynamic behavior of the Meuse/Haute-Marne argillite. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth*, 32(8–14), 907–916.
- Cundall, P. A., & Strack, O. D. L. (1979). A discrete numerical model for granular assemblies. *Géotechnique*, 29(1), 47–65.
- DiPippo, R. (2016). Geothermal Power Generation: Developments and Innovation. In *Geothermal Power Generation: Developments and Innovation*. Woodhead Publishing.
- Hondros. (1959). The evaluation of Poisson's ratio and the modulus of materials of low tensile resistance by the Brazilian (indirect tensile) test with particular reference to concrete. *Aust. J. Appl. Sci.*, 10, 243–268.
- Idelsohn, S. R., Onate, E., & Del Pin, F. (2004). The particle finite element method: A powerful tool to solve incompressible flows with free-surfaces and breaking waves. *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, 61(7),
- Idelsohn, Sergio R., & Oñate, E. (2006). To mesh or not to mesh. That is the question... *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, 195(37–40), 4681–4696.
- Larsson, S., Prieto, J. M. R., Heiskari, H., Jonsén, P., Rodríguez Prieto, J., Heiskari, H., & Jonsén, P. (2021). A Novel Particle-Based Approach for Modeling a Wet Vertical Stirred Media Mill. *Minerals*, 11(1), 55.
- Livermore Software Technology Corporation. (2014). *ICFD THEORY MANUAL Incompressible fluid solver in LS-DYNA*.
- Livermore Software Technology Corporation, (2020). *LS-Dyna Keyword user's manual volume 1 (R12)*.
- Melamed, Y., Kiselev, A., & Gelfgat, M. (1997). Hydraulic Hammer Drilling Technology: Developments and Capabilities. *Annual International Energy Week Conference*, 8.
- Plinninger, R. J. (2008). Abrasiveness Assessment for Hard Rock Drilling. *Geomechanik Und Tunnelbau*, 1(1), 38–46.
- Potyondy, D. O., & Cundall, P. A. (2004). A bonded-particle model for rock. *International Journal of Rock Mechanics and Mining Sciences*, 41(8 SPEC.ISS.), 1329–1364.
- Saadati, M. (2015). *On the mechanical behavior of granite : Constitutive modeling and application to percussive drilling* (Issue 89). Royal Institute of Technology.
- Saksala, T., Fourmeau, M., Kane, P. A., & Hokka, M. (2018). 3D finite elements modelling of percussive rock drilling: Estimation of rate of penetration based on multiple impact simulations with a commercial drill bit. *Computers and Geotechnics*, 99(February), 55–63.
- Scholtès, L., Donzé, F. V., Donze, F., & Donzé, F. V. (2013). A DEM model for soft and hard rocks: Role of grain interlocking on strength. *Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids*, 61(2), 352–369.
- Shariati, H. (2019). *Mechanical modeling of granite subjected to contact loading*.

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